

ABSTRACT. The paper of the is to initiate the study of real AW*-algebras in the framework of the theory of real C*-algebras and W*-algebras. It happens that in some aspects real AW*-algebras behave unlike complex AW*-algebras and sometimes their properties are completely different also from corresponding properties of real W*-algebras. We prove that if the complexification $A + iA$ of a real C*-algebra A is a (complex) AW*-algebra then A itself is a real AW*-algebra. By modifying the Takenouchi's examples of complex non-W*, AW*-factors we show that there exist real non-W*, AW*-factors. The correspondence between real AW*-factors and involutive (i.e. with period 2) *-anti-automorphisms of (complex) AW*-factors is established. We give the decomposition of real AW*-algebras into types *I*, *II* and *III* similar to the case of complex AW*-algebras or W*-algebras. It is proved that if A is a real AW*-factor and its complexification $M = A + iA$ is also an AW*-algebra (and therefore an AW*-factor) then the types of A and M coincide.

KEYWORDS: AW*-algebra, C*-algebra, factor, involutive *-antiautomorphism, complex Hilbert space, commutant, complexification, linear *-automorphism, conjugate, bicommutant, quaternions algebra, projection, isomorphic.

1. INTRODUCTION

The theory of operator algebras was initiated in a series of papers by Murray and von Neumann in thirties. Later such algebras were called von Neumann algebras or W*-algebras. These algebras are self-adjoint unital subalgebras M of the algebra $B(H)$ of bounded linear operators on a complex Hilbert space H , which is closed in the weak operator topology. Equivalently M is a von Neumann algebra in $B(H)$ if it is equal to the commutant of its commutant (von Neumann's bicommutant theorem). A factor (or W*-factor) is a von Neumann algebra with trivial center and investigation of general W*-algebras can be reduced to the case of W*-factors, which are classified into types *I*, *II* and *III*.

Real operator algebra is a *-algebra consisting of bounded (real) linear operators on a real Hilbert space H . If it is closed in the weak operator topology we have real W*-algebra, and if it is uniformly closed (i.e. in the norm topology) then we come to the notion of the real C*-algebra.

In his monograph [7] Li Bing-Ren has set up the fundamentals of real operator algebras and gave a systematic discussion of the real counterpart for the theory of W*- and C*-algebras.

A slightly different (but almost the same up to *-isomorphism) definition of real W*-algebras was given by E. Størmer [13,14]: A real von Neumann algebra (or real W*-algebra) is a real *-algebra \mathfrak{R} of bounded linear operators on a complex Hilbert space containing the identity operator $\mathbf{1}$, which is closed in the weak operator topology and satisfies the condition $\mathfrak{R} \cap i\mathfrak{R} = \{0\}$. The smallest (complex) von Neumann algebra $U(\mathfrak{R})$ containing \mathfrak{R} coincides with its complexification $\mathfrak{R} \cap i\mathfrak{R}$, i.e. $U(\mathfrak{R}) = \mathfrak{R} \cap i\mathfrak{R}$. Moreover \mathfrak{R} generates a natural involutive (i.e. of order 2) *-antiautomorphism $\alpha_{\mathfrak{R}}$ of $U(\mathfrak{R})$, namely $\alpha_{\mathfrak{R}}(x + iy) = x^* + iy^*$, where $x + iy \in U(\mathfrak{R})$, $x, y \in \mathfrak{R}$. It is clear that $\mathfrak{R} = \{x \in U(\mathfrak{R}) : \alpha(x) = x^*\}$. Conversely, given a (complex) von Neumann algebra U and any involutive *-antiautomorphism α on U , the set $\{x \in U : \alpha(x) = x^*\}$ is a real von Neumann algebra in the above sense.

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It is not difficult to see that two real von Neumann algebras generating the same (complex) von Neumann algebra are isomorphic if and only if the corresponding involutive $*$ -antiautomorphisms are conjugate. Thus the study of the above real von Neumann algebra can be reduced to the study of pairs (U, α) , where U is a (complex) von Neumann algebra and α - its involutive $*$ -antiautomorphism.

2. PRELIMINARIES

Let H be a complex Hilbert space, $B(H)$ denote the algebra of all bounded linear operators on H . The *weak (operator) topology* on $B(H)$ is the locally convex topology, generated by semi norms of the form: $\rho(a) = |(\xi, a\eta)|$, $\xi, \eta \in H$, $a \in B(H)$. W^* -algebra is a weakly closed complex $*$ -algebra of operators on a Hilbert space H containing the identity operator $\mathbf{1}$. Recall that W^* -algebras are also called *von Neumann algebras*.

Let further M be a W^* -algebra. The set M' of all elements from $B(H)$ commuting with each element from M is called the commutant of the algebra M . The *center* $Z(M)$ of a W^* -algebra M is the set of elements of M , commuting with each element from M . It is easy to see that $Z(M) = M \cap M'$. Elements of $Z(M)$ are called *central* elements. A W^* -algebra M is called *factor*, if $Z(M)$ consists of the complex multiples of $\mathbf{1}$, i.e. if $Z(M) = \{\lambda\mathbf{1}, \lambda \in \mathbb{C}\}$. We say that a W^* -algebra M is *injective* if there exists a projection P in $B(H)$ onto M such that $\|P\| = 1$ and $P(\mathbf{1}) = \mathbf{1}$. This is equivalent to the condition that M is *hyperfinit*, i.e., that there exists an increasing sequence $\{M_n\}$ of matrix subalgebras of the algebra M containing $\mathbf{1}$ and such that the union $\cup_n M_n$ is weakly dense in M .

Let e, f, h be projections from M . We say that e is equivalent to f , and write $e \sim f$, if $e = \omega^* \omega$, $f = \omega \omega^*$ for some partial isometry ω from M . A projection e is called: *finite*, if $e \sim f \leq e$ implies $f = e$; *infinite* - otherwise; *purely infinite*, if e doesn't have any nonzero finite subprojection; *abelian*, if the algebra eMe is an abelian W^* -algebra. A W^* -algebra M is called *finite*, *infinite*, *purely infinite*, if $\mathbf{1}$ is a finite, infinite, purely infinite respectively; M is σ -finite, if any family of pairwise orthogonal projections from M is at most countable; *semifinite*, if each projection in M contains a nonzero finite subprojection; *properly infinite*, if every nonzero projection from $Z(M)$ is infinite; *discrete*, or of type *I*, if it contains a faithful abelian projection (i.e. an abelian projection with the central support $\mathbf{1}$); *continuous*, if there is no abelian projection in M except zero; M is of type *II*, if M is semifinite and continuous; type I_{fin} (respectively I_∞), if M is of type *I* and finite (respectively properly infinite); type II_1 (respectively type II_∞), if M is of type *II* and finite (respectively properly infinite); type *III*, if M is purely infinite. It is known that any W^* -algebra has a unique decomposition along its center into the direct sum of W^* -algebras of the I_{fin} , I_∞ , II_1 , II_∞ and *III* types.

A linear mapping $\alpha : M \rightarrow M$ is called a $*$ -*automorphism* (respectively a $*$ -*antiautomorphism*) if $\alpha(x^*) = \alpha(x)^*$ and $\alpha(xy) = \alpha(x)\alpha(y)$ (respectively $\alpha(xy) = \alpha(y)\alpha(x)$), for all $x, y \in M$. A mapping α is called *involutive* if $\alpha^2 = id$. A $*$ -automorphism α is called *inner* if there exists a unitary u in M , such that $\alpha(x) = u x u^*$, for all $x \in M$. A $*$ -automorphism is called *centrally trivial* if

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$\alpha(x_n) - x_n \rightarrow 0$ *-strongly as $n \rightarrow \infty$ for any central sequence $\{x_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$. We shall denote by $Aut(M)$ the group of all *-automorphisms, by $Aut(M)$ the group of all *-antiautomorphisms, by $Int(M)$ the group of all inner *-automorphisms, and by $Ct(R)$ the subgroup of its centrally trivial *-automorphisms of M . Two *-automorphisms or *-antiautomorphisms α and β are said to be conjugate (or outer conjugate), if $\alpha = \theta \cdot \beta \cdot \theta^{-1}$ (respectively $Adu \cdot \alpha = \theta \cdot \beta \cdot \theta^{-1}$) for some *-automorphism θ (and an inner *-automorphism Adu). A linear functional ω on M is called *positive*, if $\omega(x^*x) \geq 0$ for all $x \in M$. A positive linear functional ω on M with $\|\omega\| = 1$ is called a state. Let M_+ be the positive part of M . A weight on M is a homogeneous additive function $\omega: M_+ \rightarrow [0, +\infty]$ (we suppose that $0 \cdot +\infty = 0$). A weight (or a state) ω is called: *faithful*, if for any $x \in M_+$, $\omega(x) = 0$ implies $x = 0$; *normal*, if for any net $\{x_\alpha\}$ in M , increasing to an element x , we have $\omega(x) = \sup_\alpha \omega(x_\alpha)$; *finite*, if $\omega(x) < \infty$ for all $x \in M_+$; *semifinite*, if for any $x \in M_+$ there exists a net of elements $\{y_\alpha\} \in M_+$, such that $\omega(y_\alpha) < \infty$, and $y_\alpha \rightarrow x$ in σ -weak topology; ω is a trace, if $\omega(uxu^*) = \omega(x)$ for all $x \in M_+$ and each unitary $u \in M$.

The type of a W^* -algebra is tightly connect with the existence of traces on it. Namely a W^* -algebra M is a finite if and only if it possesses a separating family of finite normal traces; it is semifinite if and only if it possesses a faithful semifinite normal trace; M is purely infinite if and only if there is no nonzero semifinite normal trace on M (see [15]).

Definition. [4]. By a real C^* -algebra we mean a real Banach *-algebra R such that the relation $\|a^*a\| = \|a\|^2$ holds and the element $1 + a^*a$ is invertible for any $a \in R$.

Definition*. [8,9]. A real C^* -algebra R such that $R + iR$ is a complex W^* -algebra is referred to as a real W^* -algebra.

We proceed with another definition of a real W^* -algebra, which can be found in papers of Størmer.

Definition. [2,13].** A unital weakly closed real *-algebra R in $B(H)$ such that $R \cap iR = \{0\}$ is called a *real W^* -algebra*.

A real W^* -algebra R is called a (real) factor if its center $Z(R)$ consists of elements $\lambda 1$, $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$. We say that a real W^* -algebra R is of type I_{fin} , I_∞ , II_1 , II_∞ and III , $\lambda \in [0, 1]$ if the enveloping W^* -algebra $U(R) = R + iR$ (i.e., the least W^* -algebra containing R) is of the corresponding type with respect to the usual classification of W^* -algebras.

3. MAIR RESULTS

Let A be a real C^* -algebra, with the complexification $M = A + iA$. Then M is a complex C^* -algebra and, as we have seen in the previous section, if A is a real AW^* -algebra M may not be a (complex) AW^* -algebra. Now let us consider the converse problem if $M = A + iA$ is an AW^* -algebra is A necessarily a real AW^* -algebra? The following result gives a positive answer to this problem.

Proposition 1. *Let A be a real C^* -algebra and let $M = A + iA$ be its complexification. Suppose that M is an AW^* -algebra. Then A is a real AW^* -algebra.*

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Proof. As we have mentioned in the first section, A coincides with the fixed point set under the conjugate linear $*$ -automorphism " $\bar{\cdot}$ ": $x + iy \mapsto x - iy$ of M , where $x, y \in A$, i.e. $A = \{a \in M : \bar{a} = a\}$. If S is a nonempty subset in A then for its right-annihilator (with respect to M) we have

$$R_M(S) = \{a \in M \mid sa = 0 \text{ for all } s \in S\}$$

and

$$a \in R_M(S) \Leftrightarrow sa = 0, \forall s \in S \Leftrightarrow \overline{sa} = \bar{s} \bar{a} = s \bar{a} = 0, \forall s \in S$$

because $\bar{\bar{s}} = s \in A$. This means that $a \in R_M(S)$ if and only if $\bar{a} \in R_M(S)$.

Now suppose that M is an AW*-algebra, then $R_M(S) = gM$ for a suitable projection $g \in M$. Since $g \in R_M(S)$ from above it follows that $\bar{g} \in R_M(S)$. Therefore \bar{g} is a projection and $\bar{g} \in gM$, i.e. $\bar{g} = g\bar{g}$. Thus $(\bar{g})^* = (g\bar{g})^* = (\bar{g})^* g^* = \bar{g}g = \bar{g} = g\bar{g}$ i.e. $g = \bar{\bar{g}} = \overline{g\bar{g}} = \bar{g}g = \bar{g}$. This means that $g \in A$. But then

$$R_M(S) = R_M(S) \cap A = gM \cap A = gA,$$

i.e. A is a real AW*-algebra.

Proposition 2. *There exist real AW*-factors which are not real W*-factors.*

Theorem 1. *A real AW*-algebra A is a real W*-algebra if and only if*

- (i) *A possesses a separating family of normal states;*
- (ii) *its complexification $M = A + iA$ is an AW*-algebra.*

Proof. Necessity is obvious, since if A is a real W*-algebra, then $M = A + iA$ is a (complex) W*-algebra (see [7, Chap.5]). Therefore, M is an AW*-algebra and it possesses a separating family of normal states, the restrictions of which on A give a separating family of normal states on A .

Sufficiency. Let $M = A + iA$ be an AW*-algebra and let A possess a separating family of normal states, which we denote by $\{f_\gamma\}$, i.e. for any $a \in A, a \geq 0, a \neq 0$ exists $f \in \{f_\gamma\}$ with $f(a) = 0$.

For $x \in a + ib \in M, a, b \in A$, we put $\alpha(x) = a^* + ib^*$. A straightforward calculation shows that α is an involutive (i.e. with period 2) $*$ -anti-automorphism of M , and $A = \{a \in M : \alpha(a) = a^*\}$.

The extension of f_γ by linearity on M we denote by f_γ^0 , and we shall show, that the family $\{f_\gamma^0\}$ is a separating family of normal states on M .

For $x = a + ib \in M_s = \{x \in M : x^* = x\}$ we have $a^* = a, b^* = -b$, and since f_γ is hermitian we obtain $f_\gamma^0(x) = f_\gamma(a) + if_\gamma(b) = f_\gamma(a)$, since $f_\gamma(b) = 0$. Thus, for $x \in M_s$ we have

$$f_\gamma^0(x) = \frac{1}{2} f_\gamma(x + \alpha(x)),$$

and $x + \alpha(x) \in A$, since $x + \alpha(x) = 2a$.

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If $x \geq 0$, then $\alpha(x) \geq 0$ (because α is a $*$ -anti-automorphism), and hence $x + \alpha(x) \geq 0$, i.e. $x + \alpha(x) \in A^+$. Therefore $f_\gamma^0(x) = \frac{1}{2} f_\gamma(x + \alpha(x)) \geq 0$, i.e. all functionals f_γ^0 are positive on M . Moreover, we have $f_\gamma^0(1) = f_\gamma(1) = 1$, i.e. $\{f_\gamma^0\}$ is a family of states on M .

Now let us show, that each state f_γ^0 is normal. If $\{x_\nu\} \subset M$ is an arbitrary net with $x_\nu \searrow 0$, then since α is an order isomorphism of M , we have $\alpha(x_\nu) \searrow 0$. Therefore $x_\nu + \alpha(x_\nu) \searrow 0$ and $x_\nu + \alpha(x_\nu) \in A^+$. Since f_γ is a normal we obtain

$$f_\gamma^0(x_\nu) = \frac{1}{2} f_\gamma(x_\nu + \alpha(x_\nu)) \rightarrow 0$$

i.e. all functionals f_γ^0 are normal on M .

Finally, let $x \in M$, $x \geq 0$ and $f_\gamma^0(x) = 0$ for all γ . Then $x + \alpha(x) \in A^+$, and since $\{f_\gamma^0\}$ is a separating family of states, $x + \alpha(x) = 0$. Hence we have $x = -\alpha(x) \in M^+ \cap (-M^+) = \{0\}$, i.e. $x = 0$. Thus, the AW*-algebra M possesses a separating family of normal states $\{f_\gamma^0\}$. By the theorem of Pedersen [10] M is a W*-algebra. Therefore, by [7] A is a real W*-algebra.

Now, let M be a (complex) AW*-factor, α its involutive $*$ -anti-automorphism. Then as it was mentioned above the set $A = \{a \in M : \alpha(a) = a^*\}$ is a real C*-algebra such that $M = A + iA$ (actually $\bar{x} = \alpha(x^*)$ in terms of operation "·") and from Proposition 4.3.1 it follows that A is a real AW*-factor. It is known that two real W*-algebras generating the same (complex) W*-algebra, are isomorphic if and only if the corresponding involutive $*$ -anti-automorphisms are conjugate [2,13,14]. A similar result is also valid for real AW*-algebras:

Proposition 3. *Let α and β be involutive $*$ -anti-automorphisms of a (complex) AW*-factor M . Then the real AW*-factors*

$$A = \{x \in M : \alpha(x) = x^*\} \text{ and } B = \{x \in M : \beta(x) = x^*\}$$

are real $$ -isomorphic if and only if the involutive $*$ -anti-automorphisms α and β are conjugate, i.e. $\beta = \theta\alpha\theta^{-1}$ for a suitable $*$ -automorphism of the AW*-factor M .*

Proof. Let A and B be real $*$ -isomorphic with a $*$ -isomorphism $\theta_0 : A \mapsto B$. Then θ_0 can be naturally extended to a (complex) $*$ -isomorphism θ of their complexifications $A + iA$ and $B + iB$ both coincide with M . Therefore θ is a $*$ -automorphism of M and $\theta(A) = B$, i.e. $\alpha(x) = x^*$ if and only if $\beta(\theta(x)) = (\theta(x))^* = \theta x^*$. Thus for $x \in A$ we have

$$\beta(\theta(x)) = (\theta(x))^* = \theta(x^*) = \theta\alpha(x), \text{ i.e. } \beta = \theta\alpha\theta^{-1}\alpha(x) \text{ for all } x \in A.$$

Since $\theta^{-1}\beta^{-1}\theta\alpha$ is a $*$ -automorphism on M which is identical on A and any real $*$ -automorphism of A can be uniquely extended to a complex $*$ -automorphism of M , it follows that $\theta^{-1}\beta^{-1}\theta\alpha = id$ on whole M , i.e. $\theta\alpha = \beta\theta$ and $\beta = \theta\alpha\theta^{-1}$, i.e. α and β are conjugate.

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Conversely, if α and β are conjugate, i.e. $\beta = \theta\alpha\theta^{-1}$ for a suitable complex *-automorphism θ of M , then $\theta\alpha = \beta\theta$ and $\alpha(x) = x^*$ if and only if $\beta(\theta(x)) = \theta x^* = (\theta x)^*$, i.e. $\theta(A) = B$. Therefore, θ restricted on A gives the needed *-isomorphism between real AW*-factors A and B .

Now we consider one of the main results of this section.

Theorem 2. *Let A be a real AW*-algebra and its complexification $M = A + iA$ is a (complex) AW*-algebra. Then A is of type I if and only if M of type I.*

Corollary. *Let A be a real AW*-algebra of type I, and its complexification $M = A + iA$ is a (complex) AW*-algebra. Then A is a real W*-algebra if and only if its center Z_A is a real W*-algebra.*

Proof. If A is a real W*-algebra then, obviously, its center Z_A is a real W*-algebra. Conversely, let A be an AW*-algebra of type I and its center is a W*-algebra. Then by Theorem 4.5.2, $M = A + iA$ is an AW*-algebra of type I, and its center $Z_M = Z_A + iZ_A$ is a W*-algebra. From Kaplansky's theorem [6, Theorem 2] it follows that M is a W*-algebra. Therefore, A is a real W*-algebra.

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